

Base4NFDI–Toolkit for Harmonizing Piloting and Testing Strategies

Version 1.0, 2025

Authors: Susanna Kuper, Jana Plomin

This piloting and testing toolkit provides a structured, practice-oriented resource to support service managers in effectively planning, executing, and integrating pilot projects and testing strategies throughout the lifecycle of Base4NFDI basic services. It offers curated best practices, practical methods, and supporting materials such as checklists. Its purpose is to enable informed decision-making, ensure alignment with Base4NFDI requirements, and facilitate a smooth transition from early testing phases to full-scale implementation.

Table of Contents

Inhalt

1. Introduction.....	2
2. Strategic Relevance of Piloting and Testing	4
3. Planning Piloting and Testing.....	6
4. Piloting and Testing in the Context of Base4NFDI	9
4.1 Initialisation Phase	9
4.2 Integration- and Ramp-Up Phase	12
5. Methods Overview	14
5.1 Focus Group.....	14
5.2 Survey.....	16
5.3 Qualitative Interview	18
5.4 Usage Scenarios	20
5.5 Hypothesis Testing	22
5.6 A/B Testing.....	23
5.7 Prototyping.....	25
5.8 User Testing.....	26
6. About this Guide and Further Ressources	29

1. Introduction

Early validation of new services is a crucial element in a successful development process. It empowers service managers to assess the feasibility and practical suitability of a concept right from the initial stages. By incorporating early feedback, adjustments can be made promptly—helping to optimize resource allocation and steer clear of potential pitfalls before they escalate into costly issues.

A critical aspect of this process is ensuring that the service meets real user needs. Only when a service resonates with its intended audience it can achieve lasting acceptance and success.

Across the developmental lifecycle, dedicated testing phases are essential to uncover any challenges related to the final operational environment at an early point. The practice of targeted testing and piloting offers a number of benefits:

- **Minimized Risk:** Early detection of issues significantly reduces the risk of widespread failure at a larger scale.
- **Validation of Assumptions:** Testing serves as a means to verify initial assumptions regarding functionality, user behavior, and environmental conditions, allowing for necessary adjustments.
- **Enhanced Collaboration:** Pilots provide an opportunity for development and implementation teams to work together closely before proceeding with a full-scale rollout.
- **User Insight:** Engaging a carefully selected, representative sample of the target audience delivers crucial insights into real-world perceptions, confirming whether the chosen approach is effective and generating additional ideas.
- **Informed Decision-Making:** The insights gained through testing empower managers to make strategic decisions concerning further service refinement and resource management.

Focus and Target Group

The objective of this paper is to present a comprehensive concept—a curated collection of best practices and methods—designed to ensure a harmonious and efficient integration of pilot projects and testing strategies. It is intended to equip **service managers** with the necessary insights and practical guidelines to thoroughly understand the subject and tailor piloting and testing specifically for their basic service. Furthermore, it aims to provide an overview of the Base4NFDI requirements regarding piloting and testing across the various phases of basic service development.

This document is practice-oriented, offering actionable information and support materials, such as checklists, to facilitate the planning and execution of piloting initiatives and testing phases. Through this resource, readers are empowered to streamline their processes and ultimately achieve a smoother transition from early testing to full-scale implementation.

How to use the Document

This document is structured to provide both general orientation and project-specific guidance for piloting and testing. Each chapter is designed to serve a distinct purpose:

- **Chapter 2** explains why piloting and testing are strategically important. It also introduces user-centered design (UCD) as a practical framework for embedding testing into service development. Readers can use this chapter to understand the bigger picture and to position their own work within a broader strategic context.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the essential steps for planning piloting and testing strategies. It provides hands-on guidance for choosing suitable approaches and methods depending on goals, resources, and framework conditions. This chapter is intended as a practical reference for service managers who need to design or adapt testing activities.
- **Chapter 4** builds directly on this foundation by specifying the requirements, recommendations, and responsibilities that apply within Base4NFDI. It details which methods are expected, points to supporting documents, and clarifies the roles of different task areas. Readers can use this chapter to align their planning and implementation with the shared framework of the project and see where supporting documents or task area responsibilities provide additional help.
- **Chapter 5** contains a selection of methods that are relevant for pilot projects and tests. Each method description corresponds to a practical toolkit and contains, for example, checklists, templates and planning steps. Readers can use this chapter as a toolbox to plan the methods and apply them directly in practice.

Defining Piloting and Testing Strategies

This guidance note outlines a diverse set of mechanisms designed to test services before their full implementation, with ‘pilots’ representing just one available form of implementation. A pilot project is defined as a small-scale, controlled initiative or test phase that takes place before a complete rollout. Its main objective is to evaluate, within a confined setting, how an idea, product, or methodology performs; to spot any potential issues; and to refine the strategy before it is implemented on a larger scale. For instance, a software solution might first be deployed to a limited group of users within an organization before it is made available company-wide.

In many cases, it is beneficial for organizations to employ multiple testing strategies during the early stages of project development, using the pilot phase as the final checkpoint prior to a full-scale deployment. This layered testing approach helps to ensure that, by the time a service is fully launched, any identified challenges have been addressed and the service has been optimized to meet user needs.

Testing strategies encompass the approaches and methods used to evaluate a product or service for functionality, quality, and user-friendliness. These strategies may include a variety of testing formats, such as usability testing, A/B testing, or functional testing.

2. Strategic Relevance of Piloting and Testing

Piloting and testing are not only operational tasks but also of central strategic relevance. They provide the opportunity to validate assumptions, reduce risks, and align services with both user needs and technical feasibility. The way piloting activities are structured, documented, and repeated determines the long-term sustainability and acceptance of a service within the Base4NFDI framework.

A key strategic approach in this context is **user-centered design (UCD)**. UCD is an iterative process that places users and their contexts at the heart of development and testing. Instead of treating piloting as a single validation step at the end of a development cycle, UCD emphasizes repeated evaluation loops throughout the process. This ensures that design decisions are continuously confronted with real usage scenarios, and that necessary adjustments are made early and systematically.

Following the principles of UCD, piloting and testing should include:

- **Understanding and describing the usage context:** identifying real conditions under which services will be applied.
- **Specifying user requirements:** translating needs into measurable and testable criteria.
- **Developing design solutions:** creating prototypes or pilot implementations that address these requirements.
- **Evaluating solutions from the user perspective:** systematically collecting feedback through usability tests, observations, or pilot deployments.
- **Iteration based on evaluation results:** repeating the cycle until the solutions meet the requirements in a sustainable and reliable manner.

This iterative approach highlights that testing is not a one-time activity but a recurring process. Depending on the stage of service maturity, evaluations may focus on different aspects—early prototypes can be assessed with small user groups through qualitative methods, while later pilots can be tested in real environments with larger and more diverse user populations.

The following schematic illustration, adapted from the [ISO 9241-210 standard](#), demonstrates the interdependencies of these activities and underscores the importance of continuous evaluation:

Figure 1: Iterative process of UCD in piloting and testing (Source: DIN EN ISO 9241-210:2019)

In strategic terms, adopting such a cycle offers three major advantages:

1. **Risk reduction:** Errors and mismatches are identified early, before full-scale implementation.
2. **Stakeholder alignment:** Continuous feedback loops ensure that diverse perspectives are considered and balanced.
3. **Sustainability:** Iterative validation supports solutions that are not only functional, but also accepted and used in practice.

Piloting and testing thus become more than technical verification steps; they are strategic instruments that shape the overall success of a service. By embedding them in an iterative, user-centered process, project teams can ensure that services remain relevant, usable, and aligned with the long-term goals of the NFDI.

3. Planning Piloting and Testing

When planning piloting and testing in a software development project, several key aspects need to be considered to ensure the resulting solution is reliable, user-friendly, and aligned with actual user needs. First and foremost, clear **overall objectives** for piloting and testing must be defined as a basis to select different approaches and activities. This may include objectives relating to functionality, usability, performance, integration, or user acceptance. Later, when the approaches and activities are defined the objectives should also be defined for the approaches and individual activities. Key questions for defining the objectives could be:

- What do we aim to assess?
- Why are these tests being conducted?
- And for what purpose will the results be used?

Moreover, it is also important to anticipate potential **limitations and challenges** early in the planning process. These might include constraints such as limited access to end users, lack of test data, time restrictions, or technical dependencies on other systems or teams. By identifying such factors in advance, project teams can adjust their expectations, plan appropriate mitigation strategies, and choose testing methods that are both feasible and effective under the given conditions.

Another important aspect is to identify the **target user group**. This process should build on the preliminary work of the requirements analysis. Base4NFDI services may involve end users from a variety of consortia, either researchers, data managers or technical staff working in repositories or data centers. The examination of actual user groups should also address how to gain access to real users and encourage their participation in pilot activities. Where relevant, consider the impact of regional differences or other differences in the test population on the results and the extent to which results can be replicated across other locations or populations.

A clear understanding of the user group forms the basis for designing meaningful test scenarios. The personas developed at the beginning of the Initialisation Phase can support this process by helping teams empathize with their users and anticipate their needs. Further information on creating a persona can be found in the [Base4NFDI - Persona Creation Kit](#). Similarly, developing user stories provides a structured way to define user goals and expectations. Detailed guidance on creating user stories is available in the [Base4NFDI – User Story Guide](#).

When to consider different test approaches and methods?

Testing **approaches** describe the overall strategy or mindset guiding how testing is conducted (e.g., UCD, proof of concept, piloting). In contrast, testing **methods** are the concrete techniques or procedures applied within that approach, such as boundary value analysis or regression testing.

Testing approaches should be proportionate to the size, complexity, and level of uncertainty involved in designing a service. They must also reflect preliminary considerations concerning objectives and constraints. One of the most influential factors in this respect is the extent to which access to real users is available. For instance, UCD can be implemented most effectively when a stable group of users is available for repeated involvement throughout the project. If such regular access is not possible, feedback opportunities need to be carefully planned and strategically integrated into the project. **Limited access to users** often increases the pressure to validate multiple assumptions within a small number of testing sessions, which in turn heightens the importance of making these sessions as effective as possible.

To address these challenges, two strategies are especially valuable:

- **Diversity of participants:** Engaging different user groups can increase representativeness and reduce dependency on a small core group.
- **Diversity of methods:** Combining approaches that involve direct interaction (e.g., interviews, focus groups, observation) with less resource-intensive techniques (e.g., surveys, remote feedback tools) can provide a broader evidence base.

It may also be beneficial to reach beyond the immediate NFDI user community. In such cases, techniques like guerrilla testing can be employed. Guerrilla testing involves gathering quick and informal feedback from people in public settings, such as trade fairs, university campuses, or other relevant environments, thereby broadening perspectives. Where specialized testing methods are needed, the [TA1 team](#) can provide targeted support.

Factors such as the overall testing objectives, existing constraints, and the degree of access to user groups also guide the **choice of methods** for piloting and testing. In addition, the choice of methods and test design should always reflect the specific project phase:

1. **Early stages** (requirements analysis, concept development): Testing focuses on validating assumptions, exploring ideas, and assessing potential solutions. Methods such as surveys, interviews, focus groups, hypothesis testing, and low-fidelity prototypes (e.g., paper prototypes) are effective for rapidly testing concepts before committing to development or realization (in case of non-technical services).
2. **Development phase:** During development, testing shifts toward refining design and functionality. Medium- to high-fidelity prototypes (e.g., wireframes, clickable mockups, A/B testing) allow teams to evaluate usability, interaction flows, and technical feasibility in an iterative way. For non-technical services, it is crucial to test concepts and implementations at different stages, either with real users in test scenarios or by applying early-stage methods.
3. **Piloting and later stages:** Once advanced prototypes or near-final realizations exist, testing in real environments becomes essential. Usability testing, pilot deployments, and reflective discussions with users (through interviews or focus groups) help refine the solution and ensure readiness for full deployment or implementation.

The following table provides a structured set of guiding questions to support the selection of suitable methods.

Checklist Category	Guiding Questions
Define the Key Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which objectives should be validated in this piloting and testing phase? - Are there already reliable insights or previous test results available? - What additional evidence or feedback needs to be collected? - Should the testing questions be analyzed from specific stakeholder perspectives? - Is it relevant to compare different viewpoints, different scenarios, user groups, or environments? - How do the current project phase and its goals shape the test focus?
Clarify Framework Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What time and budget constraints apply to piloting and testing at this stage? - To what extent are representative users available for evaluation? - Does the team have the necessary skills and tools to conduct the planned tests? - For which testing activities is external support or training required? - Are there dependencies on other project tasks or phases that affect piloting and testing? - What risks (technical, organizational, or legal) must be managed before testing starts?
Select Appropriate Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Which approaches and methods are most effective for piloting and testing at this stage? - Can a single approach or method help address several testing questions simultaneously? - Are the available resources and framework conditions sufficient to apply the selected methods effectively? - Does the chosen approach align with the objectives and constraints of the current project phase? - How will user needs and expectations be captured authentically?

Table 1: Checklist for Selecting Appropriate Methods for Testing

A selection of detailed method profiles, highlighting approaches that have proven particularly effective in piloting and testing, can be found in the [Method Overview](#). It also contains method-specific information on when the specific methodology could be used sensibly, along with templates for planning, execution, and documentation where available.

Documenting testing strategies is essential. This includes not only the results, but also a transparent record of the methods used and the associated objectives. Consider the potential outcomes of the evaluation and next steps or alternative approaches to take in the event that

the test outcomes are not fully successful, including the impact on overall project timescales. A structured yet **flexible testing strategy** ensures that feedback is both frequent and meaningful, even under constraints. By combining multiple methods, involving diverse user groups, and aligning approaches with project phases, testing can maximize its value for both development and adoption.

4. Piloting and Testing in the Context of Base4NFDI

In the context of the Base4NFDI project, a selection of objectives and activities related to piloting and testing are predefined for the different development phases. The following table summarizes the activities recommended for each phase:

Initialisation Phase	Integration Phase	Ramp-Up Phase
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide service as a prototype and proof of concept - Tests with a selected (small) group of users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct User Studies focusing on usability and user experience - Self-assessment of software quality (for the application for the ramp-up phase and at the end of the Integration phase) - Integration of the fully functional service into the workflows of at least two consortia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Self-assessment of software quality (at the end of the Ramp-Up Phase) - Final adjustments and roll out of the service on a legally compliant, secure, and sustainable basis

Table 2: Overview of Activities Across the Initialisation, Integration, and Ramp-Up Phase

The way in which these activities are designed and implemented may depend on the maturity and nature of the services. The following section provides a detailed overview of these predefined elements and outlines how piloting and testing should be approached across the various stages.

4.1 Initialisation Phase

The goal of the pilot and testing phase within the Initialisation Phase is to demonstrate the general applicability of the basic service while gathering an initial response from the user community. One output of the Initialisation Phase should be that the basic service should be provided as a prototype.

Concerning given approaches and testing activities, it is stated that the prototype should be integrated into two or three services of the consortia as a **proof of concept** (POC) and tested with a selected (small) group of users (end-users or service providers). Nevertheless, not all

services can be integrated into another service, so that this recommendation can be aligned with the specific integration objectives of the respective service.

A POC is an early-stage testing approach used to explore whether a proposed product, service, or process is feasible and has the potential to be developed into a fully functional solution. In the context of software development, a POC focuses on verifying whether key functionalities can be implemented as intended and whether the underlying idea is technically and conceptually sound. For **non-technical services**, the focus lays foremost on testing certain characteristics and conceptual aspects against user expectations and to see if they are generally performable. Regardless of whether your service is technical or non-technical, you should check, for every development step, if it is possible to get user feedback or test the service in order to develop a POC that meets the needs of its target users.

A well-designed POC helps determine whether a solution is viable in a real-world environment, going beyond theoretical validation to include practical experimentation. This typically involves identifying and addressing potential technical, logistical, or operational challenges that could hinder future implementation. For example, a POC might test system compatibility, integration with existing infrastructure, or the handling of realistic data volumes. It also helps to uncover what needs to be adjusted—functionally or architecturally—to meet the specific requirements of users and stakeholders. The considerations and development of your service design provide an important basis for prioritizing which aspects should be reviewed in the POC. [The Service Design Guide](#) gives you an overview of the service design process and important aspects to consider.

While a POC helps to validate core assumptions and provides valuable insights into whether the proposed solution can meet high-level user goals and requirements, it does not necessarily define the final delivery method, or the detailed processes needed for rollout. Instead, it lays the foundation for further development phases, such as prototyping or piloting, and should culminate in a clearer and more grounded service definition.

The specific conditions and procedures for conducting a POC are not prescribed by Base4NFDI and may vary depending on the context and objectives of the service. However, a POC typically follows a structured process consisting of **several key steps**, which help ensure a focused and meaningful validation.

- The first step is to **define the objectives and scope** of the POC. This involves clarifying what exactly should be tested or validated—such as the feasibility of a technology, the logic of a process flow, or system performance under specific conditions. The scope should be limited to core elements that are essential for validation, for example by outlining the expected capabilities, technical specifications, or targeted use cases.
- Next, it is important to **specify assumptions, success criteria, and evaluation criteria**. These criteria—such as task suitability, accessibility, added value, or system performance—serve as the basis for assessing whether the POC has met its objectives.

Clearly defined assumptions and success indicators also help in identifying necessary adjustments and in systematically evaluating outcomes. Using personas can help define the objectives, scope, and hypotheses for a POC by grounding them in the needs and behaviors of representative user profiles.

- The **planning of testing activities** follows, including the selection of appropriate methods and the detailed design of test procedures. This also involves the engagement of relevant stakeholders, such as end users or technical teams. The previously defined evaluation criteria can guide the choice of methods—for instance, the predefined user tests may be particularly valuable, as several criteria can usually be evaluated at the same time.
- Throughout the process, it is essential to **document findings and lessons learned** in a structured way. This includes what worked well, what challenges occurred, and the reasons behind these results. Technical results, user feedback, and open questions should be captured in relation to the defined assumptions and criteria. If the findings include modified requirements, these should always be systematically incorporated into the requirements analysis documentation and updated accordingly. For further information about requirements analysis take a look at the [Toolkit for Requirements Analysis Strategy](#).
- Finally, the POC should conclude with a reflection on the **conclusions and next steps**. The insights gained can be used to refine the service concept, adjust requirements, and plan further development phases such as detailed prototyping, system architecture design, or stakeholder coordination.

Base4NFDI foresees the use of **user testing** with a small group of participants as part of the development of basic services. These tests can take various forms and draw on different methodological foundations. A proven approach is to allow users to explore a prototype independently, guided by realistic use cases. In the case of non-technical services, this may instead involve a practical trial of the service offering, where typical usage scenarios are played out. A commonly used method in this context is the “Thinking Aloud” technique, in which participants verbalize their impressions, expectations, and actions while interacting with the prototype or test the service trial scenario. This provides valuable insights into user reasoning and potential usability issues. A moderator accompanies the session and asks neutral, non-leading questions to encourage adherence to the method and to clarify specific points when needed. Depending on the nature of the test object, these user tests can be conducted either on-site or remotely. This approach can be complemented by open-ended questions and standardized questionnaires, such as the [System Usability Scale \(SUS\)](#) or [INTUI](#), to systematically capture users’ perceptions of usability and intuitive interaction.

Additional supporting methods in the context of user testing include A/B testing and card sorting. In A/B testing, users are presented with at least two different versions of an interface element or design and asked to compare or interact with them ([Methode Overview A/B Testing](#)). This method allows for the parallel exploration of alternative solutions rather than

focusing solely on optimizing a single design. To remain cost-efficient, all variants should be developed quickly and with minimal resources, targeting only the most relevant elements rather than fully implemented designs. Card sorting, on the other hand, is used to improve the information architecture, for example in menus or navigation structures. Test participants are asked to group terms or functions into predefined or self-created categories.

In addition to user testing, there are **several optional methods** that can be used within a POC to validate assumptions and evaluate predefined criteria. These include interviews, surveys, focus groups, hypothesis testing, and various forms of technical testing. Each of these approaches can contribute valuable insights depending on the nature of the service and the questions to be answered. These user-involving methods can also support you in defining the scope, formulating hypotheses, and establishing evaluation criteria. Engaging with potential users early on helps to ensure that the POC is focused on the most relevant aspects, that assumptions are grounded in real user insights, and that the evaluation criteria reflect what truly matters to the target group.

In general, it is advisable to test as early as possible—ideally before a fully functional environment exists. Early validation helps to identify risks, uncover misunderstandings, and avoid misdirected investment of resources. To support early-stage testing, there are various ways to **prototype** ideas: from simple paper prototypes and wireframes to more advanced clickable mockups. For non-technical services, visual aids such as user scenarios, process sketches, or service walkthroughs can serve a similar purpose by making abstract concepts tangible and testable. Descriptions of these non-technical methods can be found in the [Method Overview](#).

If you want to evaluate service components that could potentially be applicable to be integrated in your service, you find guidance and practical advice in the [Service Evaluation Guide](#).

4.2 Integration- and Ramp-Up Phase

While the Initialisation Phase focuses primarily on the POC, a more in-depth evaluation of individual user experiences is typically carried out during the Integration Phase. This deeper analysis is based on the one hand on direct engagement with real users through **user studies**, and on the other hand, on a structured and comprehensive **self-assessment**.

A central focus in service evaluation lies on **usability**. According to [ISO standard 9241-11](#) “Ergonomic requirements for office work with visual display terminals – Part 11: Guidance on usability”, usability is defined as:

“The extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use.”

Usability is therefore a key quality attribute describing the ease of use and operability of an interactive system, such as a digital application or a website. It encompasses three main dimensions that should be maximized:

- **Effectiveness:** Can the intended goal be achieved correctly and completely using the system?
- **Efficiency:** Is the effort required to achieve the goal as low as possible?
- **Satisfaction:** Is the user free from discomfort and does the system foster a positive attitude towards its use?

The degree of usability directly influences the quality and speed of work, the health and motivation of staff, and the sustainability and acceptance of IT projects.

User studies aim to capture the user perspective on the usability of a service as well as its broader strengths and weaknesses. The user studies will be carried out by [TA2 Team](#) based on availability and team requirement, and the service teams are only required to have a supporting role. The user studies are optional but strongly encouraged to ensure the usability and accessibility of the services. More detailed information on the creation of user stories can be found in the document [Base4NFDI User Study Procedure](#). **By month 3**, the service teams should meet with TA2 to showcase the current software status and present any usability challenges or questions. This meeting helps TA2 assess study feasibility and identify focus areas like accessibility, workflow intuitiveness, or feature validation. The session also ensures both sides align on priorities and constraints so TA2 can design a tailored study plan.

In addition to testing conducted through direct engagement with users, Base4NFDI also requires a structured **self-assessment** process. To ensure **high software quality**, the service teams are asked to go through a procedure of self-assessment three times:

1. During the application for the Ramp-Up Phase
2. At the end of the Integration Phase
3. At the end of the Ramp-Up Phase

To support this process, the [TA2 team](#) provides a comprehensive checklist of relevant quality criteria, accompanied by detailed guidance. Both the checklist and the explanatory materials are available in the [Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures \(D2.1.1\)](#) on software quality. It also provides information regarding the conduct of technical tests.

Beyond software quality, the self-assessment should focus on usability principles and adapt the service design according to the findings. Detailed guidance for following these principles can be found in the notes on usability published by TA2 in the [Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures \(D2.1.1\)](#). In particular, the principle of accessibility should be evaluated iteratively throughout the Integration Phase. As a baseline requirement, services should conform to the **Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1, Level AA**. Guidance on achieving and verifying compliance is provided in the [Guidelines on Application of Web](#)

[Accessibility](#), Chapter 3. Moreover, the [Service Design Guide](#) provides a comprehensive overview of various technical and non-technical aspects that need to be considered when designing services and that can be used for self-assessment.

In addition to the provided documents, service teams are encouraged to apply further heuristics to assess usability, such as the interaction principles defined in the usability standard DIN EN ISO 9241-110. These principles provide a structured framework for evaluating aspects such as self-descriptiveness, conformity with user expectations, error tolerance, and suitability for learning—thereby ensuring that usability evaluation remains comprehensive and aligned with international best practices.

5. Methods Overview

In this chapter, we introduce each method individually with a strong emphasis on providing practical, straightforward guidance that empowers project managers to select the appropriate methods as needed.

As emphasized in Chapter 2 [Strategic Relevance of Piloting and Testing](#), methods should not be seen as isolated tools, but as elements in an iterative, user-centered cycle of piloting and testing.

Building on this perspective, the following sections introduce a set of methods that can be applied across different phases of piloting and testing.

5.1 Focus Group

Focus Group	
Short Description	A focus group is a moderated group discussion in which potential users and/or experts share and discuss their expectations, needs, or usage-related challenges concerning an application or service. Focus groups can be used both in the redesign of interactive systems and for existing solutions.
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>Focus groups are particularly valuable for evaluating prototypes or pilot implementations in a structured group setting. They allow participants to share experiences, discuss usability issues, and provide feedback on acceptance and relevance. This method helps identify common challenges, uncover differing expectations, and generate concrete ideas for refining a service before wider rollout.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When you want to gather in-depth feedback on a prototype or pilot from multiple perspectives at once. • To validate and interpret findings from usability tests or surveys through group discussion.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before moving from a pilot phase to broader deployment, to identify refinements and ensure readiness. 	
	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	3 to 5	5 to 10
Participants: Type	Users (primarily end users, may also include experts) from one or more target groups	One focus group per target group
Responsibility for Implementation	One moderator with qualifications in facilitation and discussion management	One moderator and one co-moderator qualified in facilitation and discussion management, as well as subject matter experts in the target group's field. Optionally, a note-taker.
Tip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Alternating between question rounds, group discussions, individual or small group work, and creative activities adds variety to the process and helps maintain participants' attention. ▪ To recall who said what, it can be helpful to sketch the table or seating arrangement and assign each participant a number according to their position. These numbers can then be added to statements in the transcript for clarity. 	
Template	Focus Group Template: provided by WestChester University (in English)	

Preparation

Identify and invite participants, define possible questions, plan the procedure, and prepare materials and facilities.

Discussion

In a moderated group discussion, needs, expectations, attitudes, etc. are exchanged.

Documenting Results

Record key interim steps and results.

Follow-up Discussion

Review the results promptly afterwards.

Figure 2 – Summary of the Process Flow of a Focus Group

Focus Group Checklist

- An open need has been identified regarding knowledge about future users, the user context or the quality of a service.
- Tools for recording and documenting results—such as reporting systems, software for data collection and analysis (e.g., database, spreadsheet), audio recorder, camera, notebook, or facilitation materials—have been prepared.
- Responsibilities for planning and conducting the focus group have been assigned, the objectives and agenda have been defined, and participants have been informed in advance so that everyone knows exactly what to do.

5.2 Survey

Survey	
Short Description	<p>Surveys are a standardized tool for asking users about their opinions, needs, or attitudes. They also offer a way to gather information about the usage context. Responses may be provided in open-ended form (open questions) or selected from predefined answer options (closed questions).</p>
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>Surveys are especially useful for collecting systematic feedback on prototypes or pilot implementations from a large and diverse user base. They provide quantitative evidence on usability, satisfaction, and acceptance, and allow teams to validate results from smaller-scale tests in a broader context.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When broad feedback is needed to confirm insights from qualitative methods such as focus groups or interviews.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To capture user satisfaction and perceived usability during or after pilot deployments. When evaluating the scalability and general acceptance of a service prior to full implementation. 	
	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	Approx. 10 for qualitative results > 50 for quantitative results	10 to 30 for qualitative results > 50 for quantitative results
Participants: Type	Main potential user groups	All (potential) user groups, experts
Responsibility for Implementation	One or more responsible persons from the project team	Experts or an independent third party
Tip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Allowing questionnaires to be completed anonymously tends to increase the honesty of responses. Varying the check-box logic can help maintain respondent attention throughout the questionnaire. 	

Planning

First, the survey objectives must be clarified, including target groups, promotion, medium, and duration.

Designing

Based on the objectives, questions are derived. Categorization supports structure, and the format is chosen according to question type.

Distributing

The survey should be distributed through various channels so that the largest possible number of representatives of the target group can be reached.

Analyzing

The survey is closed, and a manual or automated analysis is carried out.

Publishing Results

If possible, survey participants should receive transparent access to the results, shared through the same channels used for distribution.

Figure 3 – Summary of the Process Flow of a Survey

Survey Checklist

- Objectives have been clarified and guiding questions prepared.
- The survey has been created in a medium appropriate to the target group, enabling easy distribution and evaluation.
- Participants are informed in advance about key points such as the purpose, scope, data protection, and duration of the survey.
- The data was documented, anonymized and stored securely.

5.3 Qualitative Interview

Qualitative Interview		
Short Description	<p>Qualitative interviews make it possible to get to know users in a short time and gather relevant information on the existing problem. Through direct conversation and personal stories, careful listening, and curious follow-up questions, emotions, needs, problems, and motivations can be uncovered. This enables the development of hypotheses and solution approaches.</p>	
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>Qualitative interviews are valuable for gaining in-depth insights into how users interact with prototypes or pilot implementations. They allow project teams to explore individual experiences, uncover detailed usability issues, and identify specific barriers or enablers for adoption. Interviews are especially useful for understanding the reasoning behind user behaviors and preferences, which may not be visible through quantitative data.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When you need rich, detailed insights into user experiences with a prototype or pilot. ● To identify root causes of usability issues or unexpected behaviors. ● When validating the effectiveness of changes made between iterations. 	
	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	2–5 from the most important target group	5 per target group
Participants: Type	Main (potential) user group	All (potential) user groups

Responsibility for Implementation	Moderator.	Moderator and observer, plus a note-taker if needed
Tip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In early project phases, it can be insightful to interview users with “extreme” positions, such as strong advocates or strong opponents of an existing legacy system. “W” questions (who, what, when, where, why) help encourage users to talk about their motivations and attitudes, from which certain decisions or behaviors can be inferred. 	
Template	<p>Qualitative Interview Template: provided by Queensland Government (in English) provided by University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland (in German)</p>	

Figure 4 – Summary of the Process Flow of a Qualitative Interview

Qualitative Interview Checklist

- An interview guide for conducting user interviews has been prepared.
- The interview questions are open-ended and neutral to elicit as much information as possible about users’ motivations, backgrounds, and attitudes.
- The interview results have been documented, at minimum in the form of notes.

5.4 Usage Scenarios

Usage Scenarios		
Short Description	<p>Usage scenarios are potential use cases that describe what users are supposed to do with the application. They specify in detail which actions users should perform, which tasks they aim to accomplish, and how the system is expected to respond.</p>	
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>Usage scenarios are valuable for piloting and testing because they simulate realistic use cases that reflect how services or prototypes are expected to be applied. They help evaluate whether the service supports real user goals and workflows, highlight potential gaps or obstacles, and ensure that pilot evaluations are grounded in authentic contexts. By focusing on user tasks rather than interface details, application scenarios provide actionable insights for refinement before full-scale deployment.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When assessing whether a prototype or pilot aligns with actual user goals and workflows. • To identify potential usability barriers or mismatches between intended and real use. • When different stakeholder groups require tailored scenarios to ensure representative evaluation. 	
	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	1	5 to 10
Participants: Type	Responsible facilitator	Potential users or stakeholders and project participants. Multiple users per target group
Responsibility for Implementation	One or more responsible persons from the project team	Experts or an independent third party

<p>Tip</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ At first, it can be useful to focus on the so-called <i>Happy Path</i> or <i>Sunny Day Scenario</i>, meaning an ideal sequence in which no errors or obstacles occur. ▪ The focus should be on the goals and tasks of the users, not on the description of a user interface.
<p>Template</p>	<p>Usage Scenario Template: provided by Bentley University (in English)</p>

Planning

Identify key use cases (with user involvement if possible) and define documentation format and level of detail.

Creation

Usage scenarios may include actors, triggers, normal system responses, alternative flows, and special notes.

Review and Adaptation

Discuss with users or stakeholders to verify correctness and adjust if needed.

Figure 5 – Summary of the Process Flow of Usage Scenarios

Usage Scenarios Checklist

- The usage scenarios are chosen in such a way that they do not involve too many interaction steps. In most cases, several complementary usage scenarios are appropriate.
- Tools for recording or documenting results, such as visualization, systematization, or analysis software (e.g., flowcharts, storyboards, process models, tables), have been prepared.
- Design elements or concrete technical solutions, such as buttons or dialog boxes, are not part of the usage scenarios.
- Different scenarios are created for different stakeholders, ensuring that each group is represented appropriately.

5.5 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis Testing		
Short Description	In hypothesis testing , an assumption about the user experience or the functionality of a system is formulated and then verified through targeted tests. Hypotheses are typically tested by measuring user performance and satisfaction.	
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>Hypothesis testing is valuable in piloting and testing because it allows project teams to validate or refute specific assumptions about user behavior, system performance, or acceptance. By using controlled conditions and measurable criteria such as task completion rates or satisfaction scores, hypothesis testing reduces uncertainty and provides clear evidence to guide further design and development.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When critical assumptions about usability, performance, or acceptance need to be verified before large-scale rollout. • To evaluate whether a new feature or change delivers the intended effect. • When data-driven evidence is required to support design or management decisions. 	
	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	5–10 participants from the primary target group	10–15 participants per target group
Participants: Type	Potential user groups who are familiar with the product or use similar systems	Representative users of the target group, ideally including different levels of experience
Responsibility for Implementation	A methodologically trained moderator with experience in hypothesis testing	Moderators with solid expertise in testing methods and data analysis, supported by an additional research team for evaluation
Tip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Moderators should not influence or resolve hypotheses during the test. ▪ Hypotheses must be clearly formulated to test specific assumptions. ▪ Standardized testing methods should be used to make results more comparable. 	

Figure 6 – Summary of the Process Flow of Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis Testing Checklist

- The results are systematically recorded and subjected to an objective analysis in order to determine whether the hypotheses are confirmed or refuted.
- During the test, moderators exert as little influence as possible on the participants to ensure the objectivity of the data.
- The participants represent the target group, with a sufficient number of individuals included to generate reliable data.

5.6 A/B Testing

A/B-Testing	
Short Description	A/B-Testing is a quantitative testing approach in which two versions of a website, feature, or UI element (variant A and B) are compared. The goal is to use usage data (e.g., clicks, conversion rates) to measure which variant performs better.
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>A/B-Testing is valuable in piloting and testing because it provides objective, quantitative evidence on the performance of two or more design or feature variations. By comparing real user interactions in a live or near-production environment, A/B-Testing reveals which version achieves better outcomes in terms of usability, efficiency, or acceptance. This data-driven approach reduces uncertainty, supports informed design decisions, and helps optimize services before broader deployment.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● When deciding between alternative designs, features, or interaction flows. ● To validate assumptions about user preferences with statistical evidence.

	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	From approximately 5 users per variant or 100 users for rough trends	Several hundred to thousands of users per variant for statistically significant results
Participants: Type	Real users in live operation or in a production-like environment	Representative, preferably large-scale live traffic with clearly defined target groups
Responsibility for Implementation	UX/product team with technical support (e.g., web analytics or development team)	Interdisciplinary team (UX, data, development) responsible for test design, implementation, and statistical evaluation
Tip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure that feedback is directed specifically at visual aspects such as layout, color scheme, readability, or design conventions, not at interactions. Use mockups to conduct discussions with stakeholders and users. Iterative feedback can help identify visual weaknesses early without high development costs. 	

Figure 7 – Summary of the Process Flow of A/B-Testing

A/B-Testing Checklist

- The mockups realistically reflect the visual design of the product (colors, fonts, layout, icons, etc.).
- The participants correspond to the target group or are relevant stakeholders with regard to visual and design requirements.
- The testing setup is designed to gather feedback on design aspects without testing interactions.

5.7 Prototyping

Prototyping		
Short Description	<p>Creation and testing of preliminary versions of a product in order to validate ideas, design, and usage concepts at an early stage, gather visual feedback, and further develop them under realistic conditions. There are different forms of prototyping:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low-fidelity prototypes are simple, rough representations. Examples include wireframes, which outline structure and navigation without design details, and paper prototyping, where interfaces are sketched on paper and interactions simulated manually. • High-fidelity prototypes are more polished and interactive, such as clickable mockups or near-final digital simulations that closely resemble the final product. 	
Purpose in Piloting and Testing	<p>Prototyping is closely connected to testing, as it enables ideas to be evaluated with users before a pilot even exists. This early testing provides valuable insights and supports iterative improvements, increasing the chances of success. By creating prototypes of varying fidelity—ranging from simple sketches to interactive mockups—project teams can validate navigation, design, and interaction flows at different stages of development. Prototyping reduces risks by allowing feedback-driven refinements early, when changes are less costly, and ensures that the resulting service reflects actual user needs.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At early stages, to test ideas with low-fidelity sketches or paper prototypes before committing to development. • During concept and design phases, to validate structure and interaction flows with wireframes and clickable prototypes. • Throughout iterative cycles, to refine usability, navigation, and visual design based on structured user feedback. • Whenever rapid feedback is needed to align design decisions with user expectations. 	
	Minimum	Typical Optimum
Participants: Number	3–5 users from the main target group	10–15 participants per target group
Participants: Type	Designer or UX expert	Interdisciplinary team with clearly defined roles (test design, moderation, analysis)

Responsibility for Implementation	Designer or UX expert responsible for creating and testing the prototype	An interdisciplinary team that collects feedback and implements it iteratively
Tip	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapt the type of prototype to the project phase: paper for ideation, wireframes for structure, mockups for design, clickable prototypes for interactions. Involve users early and regularly. Each iteration should pursue a clear goal (e.g., testing navigation, validating design). 	

Figure 8 – Summary of the Process Flow of Prototyping

Prototyping Checklist

- The prototype matches the current project stage (low- to high-fidelity).
- The testing objectives are clearly defined (e.g., navigation, interactions, visual design).
- Feedback is systematically collected, documented, and integrated into the next iteration.

5.8 User Testing

User Testing	
Short Description	<p>In user testing, potential users are asked to explore the application by completing typical tasks (use cases) while being observed by usability experts for example.</p> <p>A common method in connection with user testing is the “Thinking Aloud” method, in which the test subjects are asked to verbalize their impressions.</p>

<p>Purpose in Piloting and Testing</p>	<p>User testing is valuable in piloting and testing because it evaluates how real users interact with a service or prototype while completing typical tasks.</p> <p>By combining direct observation with techniques such as the “Thinking Aloud” method, user testing reveals usability issues, highlights areas of confusion, and captures authentic user feedback. This approach ensures that the service is evaluated against realistic use cases, supports iterative improvement, and increases the likelihood of adoption.</p> <p>When to Use</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When validating usability, effectiveness, and efficiency of a service in realistic task scenarios. • To uncover usability barriers and mismatches that may not surface in surveys or group discussions. • During iterative development and pilot phases, to refine navigation, interaction flows, and overall user experience. 	
	<p>Minimum</p>	<p>Optimum</p>
<p>Participants: Number</p>	<p>3–5 participants from the primary target group</p>	<p>5 participants per target group</p>
<p>Participants: Type</p>	<p>Main (potential) user group</p>	<p>All (potential) user groups</p>
<p>Responsibility for Implementation</p>	<p>Moderators and observers with qualifications in empathy, social competence, and domain knowledge</p>	<p>A methodologically trained moderator and observer, with the addition of a note-taker</p>
<p>Tip</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ After defining typical use cases and establishing a sequence of tasks, these can be documented on a task sheet and revealed one by one. ▪ Installation of a screen recorder or a comparable tool to capture screen activity. ▪ During testing, presenting solutions or asking leading questions should be avoided. 	
<p>Template</p>	<p>User Testing Template: provided by United States government on Digital.gov (in English) provided by German UPA (in German)</p>	

Figure 9 – Summary of the Process Flow of User Testing

User Testing Checklist

- The involved users should have skills, characteristics, and experiences that reflect the spectrum of the intended user population (EN ISO 9241-210:2010).
- Based on typical use cases, individual tasks were derived and arranged in a meaningful sequence.
- During the test, the moderator exerted as little influence on participants as possible. Support was only given in relation to the test procedure itself, not the content or the application being tested. Open questions were used to encourage participants to keep talking.

6. About this Guide and Further Resources

About this Guide

This guide was developed by the Task Area 1 team as a practical toolkit that combines established methods with recommendations tailored to the NFDI context. It provides concrete guidance on how to plan and conduct a requirements analysis and supports service teams in preparing their deliverable D.TA1.1 Requirements Analysis.

The guide was authored by **Susanna Kuper** and **Jana Plomin**, both members of the TA1 team with responsibility for requirements analysis. They offer methodological support and facilitate workshops on personas, user stories, and value propositions.

Contact

Jana Plomin

jana.plomin@fokus.fraunhofer.de

References and Resources

The following resources and documents are cited or referenced throughout this guide and provide additional information:

Manske, A., & Lorenz, A.-L. (2024, März 11). Base4NFDI - Persona Creation Kit. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10805470>

Kuper, S., & Plomin, J. (2025). Base4NFDI – User Story Guide (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14998462>

Arndt, S., Ganske, A., Lehmenkühler, D. (planned publication 2025). Service Design Guide (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16306727>

Plomin, J., & Kuper, S. (2025). Base4NFDI– Toolkit for Requirements Analysis Strategy (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17245693>

Arndt, S., Ganske, A., Lehmenkühler, D., & Wittenhorst, T. (2025). Service Evaluation Guide (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15720404>

Chen, T., & Mathiak, B. (planned publication 2025). Base4NFDI User Study Procedure (Version 1.9). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17250397>

Schäfer-Neth, C., Grudskaia, A., Chen, T., & Giesler, A. (2025). Report on Base4NFDI service integration procedures (D2.1.1) (Version 2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17206953>

Neelam Vishen, Chen, T., & Kuper, S. (2025). Base4NFDI– Guidelines on Application of Web Accessibility (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15719661>